

Figure 1. Chromatograms of *P. boldus* essential oils across four seasons of the year, summer (A), autumn (B), winter (C), and spring (D). The structure of the compound on the left corresponds to α -pinene and the one on the right to eucalyptol.

Figure 2. Chromatograms of *C. alba* essential oils in four seasons of the year, summer (A), autumn (B), winter (C) and spring (D). The structure of the compound on the left corresponds to β -phellandrene and the one on the right to 4-terpineol.